

Important: your responses are considered strictly confidential and any use in publications and presentations where you may be at risk of identification is subject to your approval.

About you and your relationship with games

- Do you play games and/or have you done so in the past?
- What about video games?
- Do you consider yourself a gamer or rather a person that plays games? Why?
- What types of games and video games do you like and dislike, and why?
- As a player, how do you approach games and video games? Do you go in to play, to win, for the story, for the experience, to play together...?
- Anything else?

About your educational activity

- What kind of educator are you? What do you do? Who are your learners? What areas of knowledge and/or education do you cover? What are your typical educational goals?
- As an educator, do you use games and/or video games?
- If so, how and why? If not, why not?
- Whether you use them or not, do you think games and video games can help you achieve your educational goals? If so, how? If not, why?
- Anything else?

About games and video games in informal education and lifelong learning

- Have you ever played “educational” games or video games? If so, which ones? And did you like them? Did you think they were “good” or “bad” as games and as educational interventions? How and why?
- Self-described educational games and video games are sometimes described as “bad”. What do you think could be reasons for calling an educational game “bad”?
- You are the learner: what notions and skills would you like to learn by playing video games? And what notions and skills have you learned?
- What notions and skills do you think can be learned and practised by playing video games?
- There are different types and genres of video games: mobile, desktop, console, handheld, action, role-playing, cards, adventure... Which ones (or combinations) do you think would work well as a lifelong learning intervention, and why?
- Anything else?

About misinformation

- What is misinformation for you?
- What are the pieces that make up misinformation? What do you need to do to create effective misinformation?
- Give me an example of misinformation that affects you or makes you mad or that you care about countering. Or more than one!
- Misinformation often has roots in specific misconceptions: what are the misconceptions that contribute to this example?
- Misinformation has also more general aspects common across topics: which ones can you think of and which ones do you care about the most?
- Give me examples of games and video games that contain the theme of misinformation. They don't have to be trying to educate players against it, just have it as one of their themes.
- Now give me examples of games that aim at educating players against misinformation, directly or indirectly.
- Anything else?

About inclusion

- What does "inclusion" mean to you? What does it mean to you in an educational context, whether formal or informal?
- Inclusion in games and video games is often an afterthought. What do you think might be the reason?
- If you were to design an educational video game, how would you make it more inclusive?
- Anything else?

Everything else

- You are the expert here, what else can you tell me around education and video games?